

Impact of Digital Environment on Academic Library

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Abstract:

The present paper explains impact of digital environment on academic library. Both print and digital selection must be organized, preserved and delivered to the users in the proper manner. The libraries will continue to acquire and preserve information. They provide a wide range of technology based services. In the current electronic information environment emphasis is given to collection developing and getting access to remote collection or data based.

Keywords: Digital Environment, Intellectual Property, E-resources, Websites, Collection Development.

Introduction:

The collection development as a library activity is designed with specific purpose to provide the library with information resource that meets the appropriate needs of its clientele. Library collection development is a process of planning and acquiring a balanced collection of library material of many formats including periodicals, online resources and other media. The collections are developed by the libraries by acquiring reading material over a period of time based on assessment of the information needs of the library and their users.

In an electric environment four major trends in library and information sciences were identified; increased in end user access to computer based information resource; library use of network and telecommunication, dependency on CD-ROM based information source and, emphasis on collection management activities.

Collection Development Policy:

A collection development policy will boost the library staff for better performance and also better facilities for continuous, consistent and balanced growth as a library collection. The collection development policies exist in order to provide guidance and direction in selection process; the essential principles behind the policy are system perspective. An existing collection development policy includes selection criterion regarding the academic and research infest to be supported.

Selection:

Selection of material for a collection is one of the most creative and interesting as the libraries should first consult their organization and follow collection development policies for selection guidelines. A collection development policy is a fluid document. It must reflect the changing needs of its users. A collection development policy provided general specific formats selection criteria. A well written collection development policy typically identifies subject area in which it may be preferable to have one format over another.

Resources for Collection:

There is all kind of barriers to local collection of electronic information for instance hardware and software limitations exist for many libraries. There is also not sufficient funding to manage an electronic collection alongside the print collection. In this information rich environment, appropriate choice for what will be the chief characteristics of the information object is a major problem. Unlike print resources, decisions regarding the acquisitive of electronic resources are directly tied to the availability of or willingness to purchase settable technology to use the resource.

Selection criteria for websites:

The selection criteria for website is its evaluation, the librarian and users must examine each site i.e. Websites owner, on sponsor website, author and grades. The structure and contents of website in reference to sources, coverage and accuracy of information content, currency and timelines of content material, readability of material, quality of links to other sites etc.

Challenge:

The technological developments are creating a numbers of problems and challenges with respect to resources collection and services. The challenges of integrating electronic resource and technologies in to the process of collection development seems to be most problematic than selection, acquisition and inter institutions cooperation.

Acquisitions:

Librarian must be familiar with the potentially short shelf life of new electronic formats and products. There are several issues to be addressed when securing access to electronic materials whether to purchase for local ruffian, to acquire collaboratively or to arrange for access online as needed. If local whether to lease or purchase, whether to use a supplier or acquire directly from the publisher and negotiating terms

preferably in conjunction with the institutions contracts and purchasing units.

Intellectual Property:

A legal and policy frame work to stimulate creativity and innovation and promote the progress of a faired equitable balance of the rights and privilege of user's creators and owners.

Others:

1. Creating methods to control and access electronic recourse.
2. Maintaining and further developing access to non-English language material in digital farmer.
3. Developing a seamless in reface for information services.
4. Developing and maintaining collections.

Conclusion:

The availability of publications in electronic format has changed the complete scenario of libraries like online reference libraries, online documents ordering and online interlibrary loan etc. The changing and nature of information handling and provision is offering a dramatic impetus towards a consideration of issues that have always been basis for collection development. The duty of librarian is to expand the range of resource and services for the benefit of uses especially to include those available in the electronic for web based or web accessible information resources.

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